

A Comparative Study of Intraperitoneal Instillation of Tramadol or Clonidine along with Bupivacaine for Postoperative Analgesia Following Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy offers reduced morbidity, pain, and quicker recovery. Effective pain treatment reduces risks of complications like pulmonary embolism, deep vein thrombosis, pneumonia, and atelectasis. Bupivacaine (a local anaesthetic class of drug), has shown promising results in managing postoperative discomfort following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Tramadol, an opioid analgesic, has been found to control moderate to severe postoperative pain in patients with day surgery and inpatients. Clonidine, an alpha-2-adrenergic analgesic, can be combined with local anaesthetics to increase sensory and motor blocking effects without causing opioid side effects.

Aim: The study compares the effectiveness of bupivacaine with tramadol and bupivacaine with clonidine for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods: The study was a double-blind, randomized prospective investigation involving 90 patients divided into two groups (45 each group) aged 18-60 years who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy belonging to ASAPS 1 and 2. Group A (bupivacaine with tramadol), Group B (bupivacaine with clonidine). Hemodynamic changes and post-operative pain scores were recorded and statistical analysis performed.

Results: The study found no significant differences in gender, age, ASA grade, weight, height, or operation duration between the two groups. The mean diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, and heart rate were comparable across the groups.

Conclusion: The study reveals that clonidine and bupivacaine offer superior postoperative analgesia during laparoscopic cholecystectomies without significant differences in hemodynamic parameters, indicating the need for further research on optimal drug concentration.

Keywords: Intraperitoneal, Tramadol, Clonidine, Bupivacaine.

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Introduction

Laparoscopy is a popular alternative to open surgery, particularly for gall bladder procedures like cholecystectomy, offering reduced morbidity, pain, and quicker recovery. [1,2]

Post-laparoscopy shoulder pain often arises from pneumoperitoneum irritation, while abdominal pain can result from inflammation, visceral pain, parietal peritoneum stretching, and blood irritability. [3,4] Studies reveal patients post-cholecystectomy experience various types of pain, with parietal discomfort being the most common, varying in severity, latency, and duration. [5]

Effective pain treatment reduces risks of complications like pulmonary embolism, deep vein thrombosis, pneumonia, and unnecessary

investigations. Postoperative pain can range from mild to severe, with intensity higher immediately. Additional complications like vomiting and nausea occur within 24 hours. [6-9] Anti-inflammatory medications, pain relievers, and analgesics can alleviate postoperative pain. Local anaesthetics can be injected, with sympathetic opioids being the preferred treatment due to their receptor binding. [10-13]

Opioids can cause adverse effects like pruritus, ileus, nausea, vomiting, drowsiness, and urine retention, leading to longer hospital stays and less successful patient outcomes. Local anaesthetic wound infiltration can reduce opioid usage and pain, with studies showing significant pain reduction. [14,15,16]

Local anaesthetics are injected intraperitoneally to provide analgesia around the surgical site, potentially reducing the severity of shoulder pain caused by gaseous distension and irritation of diaphragmatic innervations. [17] Bupivacaine is a mild local anesthetic with minimal adverse effects, especially when combined with opioids, resulting in a shorter duration of analgesia. [6] Intraperitoneal injections of local anesthetics, tenoxicam, clonidine, and other medications have shown promising results in managing postoperative discomfort following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. [18, 19,20] Narchi et al.'s 1991 study suggested subcutaneous injection of local anaesthetics post-laparoscopy, showing a decrease in discomfort compared to intraperitoneal bupivacaine or morphine administration. [21]

Tramadol is an opioid analgesic that acts on μ -opioid receptors, reducing pain. Its racemic mixture of positive and negative enantiomers inhibits serotonin and noradrenaline reuptake, releasing serotonin. O-demethylate, a potent μ -opioid receptor metabolite, is six times more potent than tramadol, causing analgesia. [45] Tramadol is a mild inhibitor of noradrenaline and serotonin reuptake and a weak opioid agonist, with its dual mode of action due to its (+)-enantiomer's higher affinity for the μ -receptor. [46]

Tramadol, an opioid, has been found to control moderate to severe postoperative pain in patients with day surgery and inpatients. It does not impact cardiovascular or respiratory variables, making it suitable for patients with impaired hepatic or renal function, the elderly, overweight individuals, smokers, and those with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications. It can be delivered orally or intravenously to alleviate pain during surgical operations. [47] Alpha-2-adrenergic analgesia, a long-term study, began with cocaine and progressed to dexmedetomidine and noradrenaline. Clonidine, a long-known alpha-2-agonist, was first used for anaesthesia in 1984. Its combination with other anesthetics offers various advantages, including sedation, hypnosis, analgesia, opioid reduction, and anti-sympathetic response to surgical trauma. [5] Clonidine, when administered intrathecally, has visible effects and can be combined with local anaesthetics to increase sensory and motor blocking effects without causing opioid side effects. A meta-analysis found that clonidine lengthens analgesia, decreases morphine rescue quantity, and increases the interval between analgesic need and duration.

However, intraoperative hypotension is the most prominent side effect. The study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of bupivacaine in combination with intraperitoneal injections of clonidine or tramadol for postoperative analgesia after laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: A double-blind, randomised, prospective investigation.

Study Location: GS Medical College and Hospital in Department of Anaesthesia, Pilkhuwa, Hapur, (Uttar Pradesh).

Sample Size: Ninety patients aged 18-60, with physical status I and II, underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, divided into two groups of 45 patients each.

The study used a web-based calculator from the University of British Columbia (UBC) to calculate the sample size based on the principle of inference for means. The pilot study involved 10 subjects, with the mean pain score in each group being 3.25 and 2.53. The sample size was estimated to be 42, with a standard deviation of 1.17 and a power of 80%. The study expanded the sample size to 45 per group to account for error and attrition.

Computerized randomization numbers were distributed in two groups: Group A received odd numbers, and Group B received even numbers, comparing intraperitoneal injections of bupivacaine and tramadol. Patients with ASAPS class 3 and above and patients with hepatic and renal impairment and pregnant women and lactating mothers were excluded from the study.

The study involved patients undergoing a laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedure, with various drugs and equipment prepared before the procedure. The patients were advised to fast for at least 6 hours before the procedure, and any loose teeth were removed. Before the procedure, baseline data such as heart rate, non-invasive blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, oxygen saturation, and electrocardiography were recorded.

The patients were pre-oxygenated with 100% oxygen and injected with propofol and succinylcholine to induce general anesthesia. After the fasciculations subsided, laryngoscopy and intubation were performed, and anesthesia was maintained with vecuronium bromide, oxygen, nitrous, and isoflurane. The patients were placed on a ventilator with a tidal volume of 8-10 ml/kg, a respiratory rate of 15 breaths per minute, a 1:2 inspiratory to expiratory ratio, a PEEP of 2, and an end-tidal CO₂ range of 35 to 45 mmHg.

Postoperatively, patients were provided with 15mg/kg of IV paracetamol if their NRS score was greater than 3. The time to first request for analgesia and total amount of rescue analgesia required by each group within a 24-hour period were calculated to gather data on the quality of analgesia. Any adverse effects that occurred postoperatively were observed and recorded for statistical analysis.

The study used SPSS 22.00 for Windows for statistical analysis, averaging each group's measurements and calculating standard deviations. The mean, represented by the letter x, evaluates central tendency and can be used with continuous or discrete data. The standard deviation measures the dispersion of data values. The chi-square test, also known as a χ^2 test, confirms the null hypothesis if the expected and observed frequencies differ significantly. Student t-tests, conducted under the null hypothesis, are used to determine if two datasets are drastically different. These tests are commonly used when an estimate is used to replace an unknown scaling component.

Results

A study involving 90 patients aged 18-60 at GS Medical College and Hospital in Uttar Pradesh aimed to determine the effectiveness of intraperitoneal instillations of bupivacaine, clonidine, and tramadol in reducing postoperative pain following elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedures. Statistical analysis included t-test and chi-square test. The study randomly assigned 90 patients to Group A and Group B based on demographics, age, sex, weight, height, ASA status, and operation length, revealing similar baseline characteristics among the research groups.

Table 1: Demographic profile among the study groups

Variables	Group A (B+T)		Group B (B+C)		p value
	N=45	%	N=45	%	
Gender					
Male	13	28.89	18	40.00	0.71 ^β
Female	32	71.11	27	60.00	
Age in years (Mean±SD)	28.77±12.87		26.63±13.76		0.64 ^λ
ASA Grade					
Grade I	21	46.67	19	42.22	0.61 ^β
Grade II	24	53.33	26	57.78	
Weight in kg (Mean±SD)	59.83±11.38		60.98±9.58		0.36 ^λ
Height in cm (Mean±SD)	164.22±11.34		162.41±11.77		0.48 ^λ
Duration of Surgery (Mean±SD)	51.43±10.87		54.52±11.69		0.47

^λ: t test, ^β: Chi square test

The study found no statistically significant differences in gender, age, ASA grade, weight, height, or duration of surgery between the two groups.

The chi-square test showed that there was more females in both groups, and the average age was 28.77±12.87 years for Group A and 26.63±13.76 years for Group B. The ASA grade II prevalence

was over 53% in both groups. The mean weight was 60 kg, and the mean height was about 162 cm. The duration of surgery was comparable in both groups.

Tables display changes in hemodynamic parameters such as systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, and heart rate.

Table 2: Comparison of SBP (Systolic blood pressure) among the groups at different intervals

Interval	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline (Before induction)	127.9	8.1	129.2	9.5	0.48
30 min after surgery	119.0	9.8	123.2	7.3	0.69
1 hr after surgery	114.0	10.6	119.9	8.1	0.35
2 hr after surgery	104.2	9.2	113.9	6.0	0.09
4 hr after surgery	111.5	7.7	116.1	6.4	0.62
6 hr after surgery	125.8	8.0	120.2	6.7	0.67
12 hr after surgery	128.6	7.2	125.17	6.3	0.78
24 hr after surgery	134.2	8.7	136.8	9.6	0.39

The comparison of SBP between the research groups at various intervals is displayed in Table 2. Tables display changes in hemodynamic parameters such as systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, and heart rate.

Table 3: Comparison of DBP (Diastolic blood pressure) among the groups at different intervals

Interval	Group A	Group B	p value
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	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline (before induction)	81.66	8.43	83.67	9.71	0.58
30 min after surgery	90.19	9.78	86.77	10.33	0.16
1 hr after surgery	85.19	10.52	82.32	10.96	0.61
2 hr after surgery	82.72	10.07	79.11	12.11	0.89
4 hr after surgery	79.26	10.59	74.05	11.2	0.32
6 hr after surgery	76.46	10.74	70.57	11.82	0.79
12 hr after surgery	75.92	10.65	71.12	10.2	0.77
24 hr after surgery	97.09	8.46	94.79	8.88	0.49

The comparison of DBP between the research groups at various intervals is displayed in Table 3. The study found that mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) increased until 30 minutes after surgery in group A, and then dropped after 30 minutes and

remained within the normal range for 12 hours. In group B, mean DBP was 83.67 ± 9.71 , and both groups' mean DBP increased until 30 minutes after surgery. DBP was comparable across the research groups at every interval where $p > 0.05$.

Table 4: Comparison of MAP (Mean Arterial pressure) among the groups at different intervals

Interval	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline(before induction)	95.73	6.55	96.69	7.73	0.18
30 min after surgery	106.04	6.42	100.83	8.22	0.29
1 hr after surgery	101.15	6.74	95.98	7.93	0.24
2 hr after surgery	97.88	6.53	92.59	9.25	0.33
4 hr after surgery	93.55	7.18	90.02	8.79	0.2
6 hr after surgery	89.37	7.44	85.83	12.08	0.1
12 hr after surgery	81.26	7.84	78.19	7.87	0.58
24 hr after surgery	104.87	7.13	103.48	7.01	0.75

The comparison of MAP between the research groups at various intervals is displayed in Table 4. The study found that mean arterial pressure (MAP) increased after surgery in both Group A and Group B. The mean MAP increased for 30 minutes after

surgery, dropped after 30 minutes, and remained within the proper range for 12 hours.

The study concluded that MAP was comparable between the research groups during all intervals.

Table 5: Comparison of heart rate among the groups at different intervals

Interval	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline (before induction)	82.57	9.34	84.58	10.62	0.69
30 min after surgery	88.1	10.69	87.68	11.24	0.23
1 hr after surgery	86.1	11.43	83.23	11.87	0.38
2 hr after surgery	83.63	10.98	80.02	13.02	0.30
4 hr after surgery	80.17	11.5	79.96	12.11	0.77
6 hr after surgery	77.37	11.65	76.48	12.73	0.64
12 hr after surgery	76.83	11.56	73.03	11.11	0.41
24 hr after surgery	74.02	9.37	73.01	9.79	0.82

The comparison of heart rate between the research groups at various intervals is displayed in Table 5. The study found that heart rates increased after surgery in both group A and group B. The mean heart rate increased until 30 minutes after surgery,

then dropped after 30 minutes and remained within the normal range for 12 hours. Both groups had similar heart rates at every interval where $p > 0.05$. The study suggests that heart rate is comparable among research groups.

Table 6: NRS score among the study groups postoperatively

NRS	Group A		Group B		t test	p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
0 min (immediately after surgery)	2.67	1.34	2.59	1.13	0.48	0.77
30 min	2.88	1.07	2.81	1.35	0.40	0.83
1 hr	2.95	1.01	2.90	1.1	0.33	0.88
2 hr	2.96	1.01	2.89	1.1	0.33	0.88
4 hr	3.69	0.96	2.72	0.87	4.05	0.016*
6 hr	3.57	1.35	2.53	0.98	3.94	0.028*
12 hr	2.91	1.14	2.45	1.02	1.07	0.35
24 hr	2.92	1.08	2.26	1.17	0.64	0.61

*: statistically significant

The study participants' level of pain was measured using the numeric rating scale (NRS). The study found that pain scores increased in both groups after surgery, with tramadol group experiencing a higher pain score at 4 and 6 hours postoperatively.

However, clonidine group experienced a lower pain score at 12 and 24 hours postoperatively. Both groups reported comparable pain levels up to two hours post-surgery. No significant difference was found in pain levels after 12 and 24 hours.

Table 7: Comparison of analgesic characteristics in both the groups

Characteristics	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Time to First Dose of Analgesic (hr)	4.23	1.37	4.91	1.08	0.043*
Total Amount of Analgesia Required in 24 hr (g)	2.4	0.73	1.43	0.68	0.037*

*: statistically significant

The study found a significant difference in the time needed for analgesia in groups A (tramadol) and B (clonidine) after 4.23 and 4.91 hours, respectively, with clonidine requiring less analgesia overall.

Table 8: Comparison of side effects observed in both the groups after the operative period

Side Effects	Group A		Group B		p value
	N	%	N	%	
Nausea	10	22.22	7	15.56	0.059
Vomiting	6	13.33	4	8.89	0.36
Shivering	2	4.44	1	2.22	0.48
Headache	1	2.22	1	2.22	1
Dizziness	2	4.44	1	2.22	0.67
Dry Mouth	3	6.67	2	4.44	0.83

Table 8 show post-operative side effects of tramadol, with nausea and vomiting being the most common symptoms, with statistically comparable symptoms.

Discussion:

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a common gall bladder procedure, but persistent postoperative discomfort and shoulder tip discomfort can delay patient discharge from the hospital. [22] Gaseous distension can cause diaphragmatic straining and phrenic nerve irritation, causing shoulder pain. Intraperitoneal instillation can alleviate this pain around the surgical site. [23]

A prospective study comparing the efficacy of intraperitoneal instillation of bupivacaine with tramadol and bupivacaine with clonidine for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy in Uttar Pradesh, India, compared the overall amount of analgesic required in the first 24 hours after surgery to the time it takes to first request rescue analgesia. The

study included ninety patients from ASA grades I and II, with the research population being individuals from ASA grades I and II. Patients with higher ASA grades were excluded due to potential influencing factors.

The study found that women outnumbered men significantly in both groups, with 71% in group A and 60% in group B. The majority of patients were 20-40 years old, with an average age of 28.77 ± 12.87 years. Both groups had similar demographic characteristics, with 53% having an ASA grade of II. The mean operation length was 51.43 ± 10.87 and 54.52 ± 11.69 minutes, respectively. Dilek Memis et al.'s 2005 study compared postoperative pain after abdominal hysterectomy using bupivacaine, tramadol, and clonidine, finding no significant differences in demographic variables. [24] Thottikat Kaarthika et al.'s 2021 study found similar baseline characteristics among 108 elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy patients receiving either 0.5%

bupivacaine, dexmedetomidine, or clonidine 1mcg/kg. [25]

In 2023, Shruthi R et al conducted a randomized, prospective, double-blind study on the effects of intraperitoneal instillation of 0.25% bupivacaine with clonidine and dexmedetomidine. [26] Studies show that most workers use 0.25% bupivacaine with 100mg tramadol and clonidine in a 1mcg/kg dose. Thottikat Kaarthika et al.'s 2021 study evaluated intraperitoneal instillation of dexmedetomidine or clonidine with bupivacaine for postoperative pain, using 0.25% solution and 1mcg/kg bupivacaine. [25]

In 2016, a randomized trial compared the efficacy and duration of intraperitoneal bupivacaine-tramadol and bupivacaine-magnesium sulfate for postoperative analgesia, with Group 1 receiving tramadol and Group 2 receiving magnesium sulfate. [22] Dilek Memis et al. conducted a 2005 study on the effectiveness of intraperitoneal bupivacaine, tramadol, and clonidine combinations in alleviating pain following complete abdominal hysterectomy, with three groups receiving different doses. [24] In 2015, Usha Skhula et al. conducted a randomized, double-blind, and prospective study on the effectiveness of intraperitoneal bupivacaine, tramadol, and clonidine combinations in alleviating pain following complete abdominal hysterectomy. The study involved patients divided into three groups: Group A, which received 50ml of 0.25% bupivacaine and 5ml of normal saline; Group B, which received 50ml of 0.25% bupivacaine and 1mcg/kg of dexmedetomidine dissolved in 5ml of normal saline; and Group C, which received 50ml of 0.25% bupivacaine and 1mcg/kg of dexmedetomidine dissolved in 5ml of normal saline. [6]

The inter-group hemodynamic parameters revealed that baseline SBP, diastolic blood pressure, MAP, and HR were statistically insignificant. Postoperatively, mean SBP dropped in both groups over the next two hours, while DBP and MAP increased up to 30 minutes after surgery. Heart rate increased until 30 minutes after surgery, but dropped after 30 minutes and remained within the normal range for 12 hours. In 2005, Dilek Memis et al. conducted a similar study to determine the efficacy of various intraperitoneal bupivacaine, tramadol, and clonidine combinations in alleviating pain following complete abdominal hysterectomy. Both groups experienced a rise in mean DBP and MAP up to 30 minutes after surgery, but started to decline after 30 minutes and stay within the proper range after 12 hours. [24]

In 2021, Th. et al. conducted a similar study to determine the efficacy of bupivacaine, tramadol, and clonidine combinations in alleviating pain following complete abdominal hysterectomy. Both

groups showed comparable DBP and MAP at all intervals where $p > 0.05$ was reported. [25]

The study assessed pain levels following complete abdominal hysterectomy using a numerical rating scale (NRS). Both groups reported comparable levels of discomfort up to two hours post-surgery. The average pain score increased in the tramadol group at 4 and 6 hours post-op, but decreased in the clonidine group at 2.72. A statistically significant difference was observed when the pain ratings of groups A and B were compared using the t test.

The combination of clonidine and bupivacaine significantly reduced pain compared to the combination of bupivacaine and tramadol (group A). Clonidine's notable effect results from its increased efficacy, which is consistent with a study by Memiset al. [24] The tramadol group had a higher incidence of adverse effects, such as vomiting and nausea. However, both groups experienced similar levels of discomfort up to two hours post-surgery.

Clonidine has been shown to lower nerve action potentials, particularly in C fibers, through a method unrelated to α_2 -adrenergic receptor stimulation. It also inhibits norepinephrine release, contributing to the medication's analgesic effect. In contrast, Dilek Memis et al. found no statistically significant differences between the tramadol and clonidine groups when comparing the tramadol and clonidine groups. [24]

In conclusion, the study found that the combination of clonidine and bupivacaine significantly reduces pain compared to the tramadol group. However, the tramadol group had a higher incidence of adverse effects, including vomiting and nausea.

Conclusion

The study reveals that clonidine and bupivacaine provide superior postoperative analgesia during laparoscopic cholecystectomies, with no significant differences in hemodynamic parameters, suggesting further investigation into optimal drug concentration.

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